

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) APG_BZFP

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: APG_BZFP

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0050 A

Wavelength=1.54184

Cell: a=10.9729 (8) b=11.6532 (12) c=14.0106 (12)
 alpha=66.069 (9) beta=81.902 (7) gamma=78.865 (7)
Temperature: 293 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	1602.8 (3)	1602.8 (3)
Space group	P -1	P -1
Hall group	-P 1	-P 1
Moiety formula	C15 H10 O5, 2 (C13 H9 N O)	C15 H10 O5, 2 (C13 H9 N O)
Sum formula	C41 H28 N2 O7	C41 H28 N2 O7
Mr	660.65	660.65
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.369	1.369
Z	2	2
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	0.771	0.771
F000	688.0	688.0
F000'	690.20	
h, k, lmax	12, 13, 16	12, 13, 16
Nref	5180	5062
Tmin, Tmax	0.758, 0.970	0.933, 1.000
Tmin'	0.735	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.933 Tmax=1.000
AbsCorr = MULTI-SCAN

Data completeness= 0.977

Theta(max)= 62.977

R(reflections)= 0.0619(4099)

wR2(reflections)=
0.1817(5062)

S = 1.023

Npar= 455

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

Alert level B

PLAT230_ALERT_2_B	Hirshfeld Test Diff for	O11	--C12	.	21.5 s.u.
PLAT230_ALERT_2_B	Hirshfeld Test Diff for	O11	--C19	.	7.5 s.u.
PLAT230_ALERT_2_B	Hirshfeld Test Diff for	C12	--C13	.	23.5 s.u.
PLAT230_ALERT_2_B	Hirshfeld Test Diff for	C13	--C14	.	12.5 s.u.
PLAT230_ALERT_2_B	Hirshfeld Test Diff for	C12A	--C13A	.	15.5 s.u.

Alert level C

THETM01_ALERT_3_C The value of sine(theta_max)/wavelength is less than 0.590
Calculated sin(theta_max)/wavelength = 0.5778

PLAT029_ALERT_3_C	_diffrn_measured_fraction_theta_full	value	Low	.	0.977	Why?
PLAT031_ALERT_4_C	Refined Extinction Parameter	Within Range of	3.250	Sigma
PLAT214_ALERT_2_C	Atom C16	(Anion/Solvent) ADP max/min	Ratio	.	4.1	prolat
PLAT221_ALERT_2_C	Solv./Anion Resd 2	C Ueq(max)/Ueq(min)	Range	.	4.5	Ratio
PLAT223_ALERT_2_C	Solv./Anion Resd 4	H Ueq(max)/Ueq(min)	Range	.	4.6	Ratio
PLAT230_ALERT_2_C	Hirshfeld Test Diff for	C15	--C16	.	5.6	s.u.
PLAT230_ALERT_2_C	Hirshfeld Test Diff for	C17	--C18	.	6.2	s.u.
PLAT230_ALERT_2_C	Hirshfeld Test Diff for	O11A	--C12A	.	7.0	s.u.
PLAT230_ALERT_2_C	Hirshfeld Test Diff for	C13A	--C14A	.	6.5	s.u.
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference	C16	--C17	.	0.18	Ang.
PLAT241_ALERT_2_C	High MainResAtom	Ueq as Compared to Neighbours		.	O11	Check
PLAT241_ALERT_2_C	High MainResAtom	Ueq as Compared to Neighbours		.	C16	Check
PLAT241_ALERT_2_C	High MainResAtom	Ueq as Compared to Neighbours		.	C17	Check
PLAT242_ALERT_2_C	Low MainResAtom	Ueq as Compared to Neighbours		.	C13	Check
PLAT242_ALERT_2_C	Low MainResAtom	Ueq as Compared to Neighbours		.	C14	Check
PLAT242_ALERT_2_C	Low MainResAtom	Ueq as Compared to Neighbours		.	C19	Check
PLAT250_ALERT_2_C	Large U3/U1 Ratio for <U(i,j)> Tensor(Resd	1)		.	2.5	Note
PLAT250_ALERT_2_C	Large U3/U1 Ratio for <U(i,j)> Tensor(Resd	2)		.	2.3	Note
PLAT334_ALERT_2_C	Small <C-C> Benzene Dist.	C14	-C19	.	1.36	Ang.
PLAT334_ALERT_2_C	Small <C-C> Benzene Dist.	C14A	-C19A	.	1.37	Ang.
PLAT340_ALERT_3_C	Low Bond Precision on C-C Bonds	0.005	Ang.
PLAT355_ALERT_3_C	Long O-H (X0.82,N0.98A)	O4P	- H4P	.	1.05	Ang.
PLAT355_ALERT_3_C	Long O-H (X0.82,N0.98A)	O5	- H5O	.	1.01	Ang.
PLAT355_ALERT_3_C	Long O-H (X0.82,N0.98A)	O7	- H7O	.	1.01	Ang.
PLAT906_ALERT_3_C	Large K Value in the Analysis of Variance	3.635	Check
PLAT911_ALERT_3_C	Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L=	0.578		.	118	Report
	-8 8 0, -7 9 0, 7 11 0, 1 12 0, -6-11 1, 11 -4 1,					
	0 1 1, -8 8 1, -7 9 1, -6 10 1, -5-11 2, 2-11 2,					
	12 -1 2, 2 0 2, -8 8 2, -2-11 3, -1-11 3, -6-10 3,					
	-10 -7 3, -11 -5 3, 11 -3 3, -12 -1 3, 12 -1 3, -10 6 3,					
	-5 11 3, 1 13 3, 2-10 4, 5 -8 4, -11 -4 4, 1 5 4,					
	(88 More NOT listed: see .ckf listing file)					

Alert level G

PLAT007_ALERT_5_G	Number of Unrefined Donor-H Atoms	3	Report
	H4P H50 H70			
PLAT093_ALERT_1_G	No s.u.'s on H-positions, Refinement Reported as		mixed	Check
PLAT199_ALERT_1_G	Reported _cell_measurement_temperature (K)	293	Check
PLAT200_ALERT_1_G	Reported _diffrn_ambient_temperature (K)	293	Check
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G	Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O11	.	106.7	Degree
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G	Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O11A	.	106.9	Degree
PLAT790_ALERT_4_G	Centre of Gravity not Within Unit-Cell: Resd. #		2	Note
	C13 H9 N O			
PLAT790_ALERT_4_G	Centre of Gravity not Within Unit-Cell: Resd. #		3	Note
	C13 H9 N O			
PLAT899_ALERT_4_G	SHELXL2018 is Outdated and Succeeded by SHELXL		2019/3	Note
PLAT909_ALERT_3_G	Percentage of I>2sig(I) Data at Theta(Max) Still		81%	Note
PLAT933_ALERT_2_G	Number of HKL-OMIT Records in Embedded .res File		1	Note
	2 0 2,			
PLAT941_ALERT_3_G	Average HKL Measurement Multiplicity	2.1	Low
PLAT969_ALERT_5_G	The 'Henn et al.' R-Factor-gap value	7.453	Note
	Predicted wR2: Based on SigI**2 2.44 or SHELX Weight 17.75			Note
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G	Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density.		3	Info

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
5 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
27 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
14 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

3 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
25 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
10 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
6 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
2 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

PLATON version of 23/04/2026; check.def file version of 30/03/2026

duplicate check

No duplication found
